

Using Measures for Verifying and Improving Requirement Models in MDD Processes

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Abstract— It is well known that an appropriate requirement specification is essential for the success of software development projects. In the model-driven development context, the requirement models can be used as entry artifacts for aligning the final software products with the stakeholders’ needs. Thus, it is necessary to solve any modeling issue that may prevent the correct translation of the input requirement artifacts; *i.e.*, the requirement models need to be verified for assuring the completeness of the design (MDD-oriented) models generated. In this paper, we face this issue by presenting an approach to integrate specific measures that automate the verification of a goal-oriented requirement approach – the i^* framework – in the context of a MDD development process.

Keywords—*measure; model verification; requirements; modeldriven development*

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of requirement models into model-based development processes is suitable to obtain software products properly aligned with the stakeholders’ needs [1]. These kind of models are referred as Computation Independent Models (CIM) in MDA [2]. Thus, to achieving the integration of requirement models in MDD, it is necessary to transform these models into adequate design models (PIM models in MDA), which can be used as starting point for automatic modelcompilation processes. Certain approaches have defined guidelines to perform this transformation. In particular, we have focused our attention in the application of GORE (GoalOriented Requirement Engineering) [3] modeling into MDD processes. However, in general terms, the existing proposals consider the requirement models to already be perfectly defined for the generation of the corresponding MDD input models [4]. In real application contexts, this idealist scenario is not feasible and, hence, there exist a high risk that the resultant design (MDD) models be incomplete and wrong in relation to the original requirement specification. Thus the goal of this paper is:

To present a model-based approach for supporting the automatic verification of GORE models in the context of an MDD process.

To achieve the proposed objective, this paper presents a concrete verification approach that is based on the specification of *verification measures* that provide key information to assure the completeness of the MDD design models generated in

relation to the original requirement specification; *i.e.*, All the requirement aspects that provide information for the system design can be traced to the target MDD model.

The verification measures are also applied to improve i^* models in a specific MDD context. To do this, we selected the OO-Method MDD approach, which has been successfully applied to industrial software development [5]. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 shows the background and the related work. Section 3 presents a big picture of the transformation process defined for transforming i^* models into MDD models. Section 4 details the proposed i^* verification process. Section 5 explains how the verification measures can be used to fix and improve i^* models. Finally, Section 6 presents our conclusions and further work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In this section, the i^* framework and the MDD approach used are briefly introduced. Also, the related work is discussed.

A. The i^* Goal-Oriented Requirement Framework

In general terms, the *Goal-Oriented Requirement Engineering* (GORE) approaches are oriented to obtain the ‘what’ of the intended systems through the analysis of organizational scenarios [6, 7]. Among existing GORE approaches, the i^* framework [8] is one of the most widespread modeling and reasoning frameworks. It emphasizes the analysis of strategic relationships among organizational actors capturing the intentional requirements. The term *actor* is used to generically refer to any unit for which intentional dependencies can be ascribed. Actors are intentional, in a sense that they do not simply carry out activities and produce entities, but also they have desires and needs.

The i^* framework offers two types of models: the *Strategic Dependency* (SD) and the *Strategic Rationale* (SR). The SD model is focused on external relationships among actors. The SR model provides the internal decomposition of SD actors’ intentions. We have considered the i^* SR model to perform the integration of i^* models into MDD processes since it offers a detailed representation of the analyzed problem scenario, which provides extra information that is relevant to generate appropriate inputs for MDD processes. Fig. 1 shows an example of an i^* SR model that is a partial representation of the OO-Method case study presented in [9], which is related to the management of work requests in a Photography Agency. In order to simplify the i^* model representation, the soft goals are

omitted in the example since this i^* construct does not participate in the generation of the target MDD models. Even though a similar situation occurs for i^* goals, this constructs are represented to be consistent with the i^* framework notation. The organizational description related to the example i^* model definition is presented below:

The photography agency is dedicated to the management of photo reports and their distribution to publishing houses. This agency operates with freelance photographers, who must present a request to the production department of the photography agency. This request contains: the photographer's personal information, a description about the equipment owned, and a brief curriculum vitae. An accepted photographer is classified by the production department in one of three possible levels for which minimum photography equipment is required. The possible levels are defined by the commercial department, who establishes the price that will be paid to the photographer and the price that will be charged to the publishing house for each photo.

Fig. 1. Example i^* SR Model

In general terms, the presented i^* model shows how the *production department* depends on the reception of *work requests* (i.e., job applications) that are produced by *photographers* that want a *work opportunity*. The *work requests* are comprised by the photographer's *personal data*. The *production department* is the responsible for *refusing* or *accepting* the *received work requests* by indicating the final *work request status*. For the accepted requests a *photographer level* is assigned according to the information provided by the *Commercial Department*.

B. The OO-Method MDD Approach Overview

OO-Method is an MDD approach that allows the automatic code generation from the conceptual representation of software systems (see Fig. 2). This conceptual representation is defined according to the OO-Method Conceptual Model, which captures the static and dynamic properties of the system in a *Class Model*, a *Dynamic Model*, and a *Functional Model*. This conceptual model also allows the specification of the user interfaces in an abstract way through the *Presentation Model*.

Fig. 2. The OO-Method Software Production Process

From the four models that comprise the OO-Method Conceptual Model, the class model is the most important. The other models are defined (or derived) from this central model. For this reason, the OO-Method class model has been considered to evaluate the approach proposed in this paper. Details about OO-Method and its industrial implementation, called Integranova, can be found in [5, 10, 11].

C. Related Work

As we can observe in the systematic review about requirement engineering and MDD presented in [12], several approaches have encouraged the use of high-level analysis models (i.e., requirement models) as part of a sound MDD process. A representative example is the MDA approach [2], which proposes the definition of a *Computation-Independent Model (CIM)* as starting point of the development process. However, most of the current requirement approaches are not automatically applied, or are not based on modeling standards [13]. Thus, an effective solution that includes requirement models as part of a complete, standardized, and automatic MDD process [14] is still an unsolved challenge [12].

Probably, one of the main issues to achieve this requirement modeling and MDD linkage is the proper definition of the requirement models for the automatic generation of domainspecific models [15] related to MDD processes. This corresponds to the transformation of CIM-to-PIM (Platform Independent Model) according to the MDA standard. Most of the proposals oriented to translate requirement models into design models or PIMs (e.g. [16] [17]) are considering the input requirement models to be properly defined to perform the translation. This idealist scenario is not applicable in practice, and verification mechanisms are necessary to assure the correct generation of the MDD models involved. To assure the automatic requirement transformation, certain proposals suggest the manual translation of the defined requirement documents to a specific computable format [18, 19]. These approaches restrict the flexibility of the original specification, which, together with the manual translation of the requirements, may cause loss of information. Other approaches suggest to add quantitative information to existent requirement modeling approaches [20-22], which allows the automatic measure and analysis of the defined models without restricting their original specification. However, there is a lack of measures to support the verification of requirement models for generation of domainspecific models (design or PIM models) [15] related to MDD processes. Hence, to fill this gap, we have considered the approaches related to object-oriented models verification [23, 24], and definition of measures to verify the correct compilation of domain-specific models [25]. Thus, in this in this paper, we present a systematic approach for the definition of automatic verification measures related to

requirement models, which support the automatic generation of MDD-oriented design models.

III. TRANSFORMING i^* MODELS INTO CLASS MODELS

In this section, we briefly introduce our proposal for the transformation of i^* models into MDD models (presented in [26]), which provide the basis for the verification approach defined in this paper.

For the transformation of an i^* model, we assume that it is possible to partially infer an *initial MDD model* from both the information that is represented in the i^* model and from extra information that is added when it is necessary (see Fig. 3). This MDD model generation is feasible if there is a mapping from i^* constructs (actors, tasks, etc.) to constructs of the MDD modeling language (e.g., for a class model: classes, attributes, etc.). The abstract syntax of the involved constructs is represented by means of the corresponding metamodels. It is important to note that we are referring to an initial MDD model and not a complete MDD model because there are aspects related to specific system functionality that cannot be obtained from i^* models. These aspects must be specified later in the refinement of the initial MDD model that is obtained.

Fig. 3. General i^* and MDD transformation schema

The i^* model transformation can be automated by means of well-defined model-to-model transformations by using technologies such as ATL [27] or QVT [28]. For the representation of the extra information that is required, we use light weight extensions, which are defined by means of a process that generates them automatically [29]. This transformation approach has been applied to a particular MDD proposal, the OO-Method approach [5], but it can be applied to other object-oriented MDD approaches with minor changes. Table I summarizes a representative subset of transformation guidelines (adapted from [30]) for i^* and OO-Method, which have been selected due to their applicability to other MDD approaches based on class model specification. These guidelines are used to exemplify the proposed verification approach throughout this paper. The rationale of these guidelines has been presented in [30]. Table I shows the i^* constructs that are involved in the transformation, the additional information that is required to perform the transformation and the target constructs of the class model.

The guidelines presented in Table I can be combined, for example, a physical resource that is a *dependum* in a dependency link generates a class, but also, associations between the classes that own the services generated from the involved tasks.

TABLE I. GUIDELINES FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF i^* MODELS INTO OO-METHOD CLASS MODELS

i^* Construct	Additional Information	Class Model Construct
Actor		Class
Resource	Physical entity	Class
	Informational resource related to a physical resource or an actor	An attribute of the class generated from the actor or physical resource
	Informational resource inside of an actor boundary	An <i>agent relationship</i> between the class generated from the actor and the attribute generated from the resource
Task	If generates an entity (physical resource or actor)	An instance creation service of the class generated from the corresponding entity
	If affects the state of a resource	A service of the class generated from the resource or from the owner physical resource.
	If does not affect resources or generate entities	A service of the actor that contains the task
	If is decomposed in resources	Associations are automatically defined among the class that contain the corresponding service and the classes generated from the decomposed resources
	Inside of an actor boundary	An <i>agent relationship</i> between the class generated from the owner actor and the task
Resource Dependency Link		Associations are automatically defined among the class generated from the <i>dependum</i> resource and the classes that own the services generated from the involved tasks
Is-a Link		A generalization relationship is generated between the classes generated from the involved actors

For the transformation guidelines related to tasks and dependency links, when the resource involved corresponds to an informational resource, the rule is applied to the physical resource related to the informational resource. For instance, a task that affects the state of an informational resource is transformed into a service of the class generated from the physical resource that owns the attribute generated from the informational resource.

In the transformation guidelines presented in Table I it is possible to observe a specific OO-Method construct: the *Agent Relationship*. This construct corresponds to a binary relationship that indicates the visibility and execution permissions that a class of the model has over other classes or over itself (recursive agent relationship). The classes that have agent relationship to other classes are named *Agents* of the modeled systems. This construct is relevant for the specification of interaction models, such as the OO-Method presentation model (see Fig. 2). Even though the agent construct is specific for OO-Method, its semantics can be generalized to other MDD approaches that define system users and interaction aspects at conceptual level. Thus, for the automatic application of the transformation guidelines it is important to determine if the defined i^* models provide a

proper specification, and, hence, the verification of the i^* models becomes necessary.

IV. INTEGRATION OF VERIFICATION MEASURES INTO THE i^* FRAMEWORK

This section explain the process for the definition and integration of verification measures into the i^* framework. For the elaboration of this process, we have considered existing standards and modeling technologies to facilitate its application for different MDD approaches. The steps of the process are described below (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Process for definition of i^* verification measures

A. Step 1: Measures Formulation

The first step of the process considers the appropriate formulation of the i^* verification measures. This means identifying the i^* constructs that participate in the MDD model generation, and, from these, identifying the aspects that must be verified for a correct i^* model transformation. To perform the identification of the involved i^* elements, it is necessary to know the transformation guidelines (or rules) related to the target MDD model generation. In particular, we focus on the additional information that must be specified by the analyst to perform the corresponding transformation, which is the critical point that must be verified to assure that the transformation can be performed correctly and automatically. The measures formulation is performed by applying the Goal-Question-Metric (GQM) approach [31]. Fig. 5 shows an excerpt of the application of the GQM approach to the transformation guidelines presented in Table I.

Fig. 5. Application of the GQM approach

For the formulation of the questions related to the GQM approach, we suggest to consider two verification levels. These levels are related to: 1) the i^* elements that must be necessarily fixed because they cannot be transformed or produce a wrong class model generation (i.e., Q1 in Fig. 5); and 2) The i^* elements that can be correctly transformed, but they still can be improved to obtain a more complete class model generation (i.e., Q2 in Fig. 5).

The verification measures formulated are specific for the transformation guidelines presented Table I. Thus, other MDD approaches will require different verification measures.

However, since we have intended to select a representative set of transformation guidelines that can be generalized for MDD-oriented class model generation, the resultant measures can provide relevant verification information to other object-oriented MDD approaches.

The measures that are related to answer the presented GQM questions are specified by considering the framework presented in [32]. This framework specifies that the empirical world, the numerical world, the measurement method, and the measurement procedure must be defined in the design of measures. In the definition of the empirical world, the entity and the attributes to be measured must be identified. An *entity* corresponds to an input artifact used to perform a measurement, and the concepts related to that artifact correspond to measurable *attributes*. In the definition of the numerical world, the measurement *scale* must be defined. In the specification of the measurement method, the *measurement principle* must be identified. Finally, in the specification of the *measurement procedure*, details of the application of the measurement method must be defined.

M1. Wrong Attribute Generation (WAG). *Rationale.* The informational resources are involved in the generation of class attributes (see Table I). Therefore, for the correct generation of informational resources, they must be related to a system entity (actor or a physical resource), which is transformed into a class in the class model. Otherwise, it is impossible to transform these resources into attributes because the class that contains them cannot be identified. Table 2 details the characteristics related to this measure according to the considered definition framework.

TABLE II. MEASURE WRONG ATTRIBUTE GENERATION (WAG)

Characteristic	Definition
Measurement Entity	i^* model
Measurement Scale	Ratio scale
Attribute to be measured	Informational resources not related to a physical resource nor to an actor
Measurement principle	An informational resource that is not related to a physical resource nor to an actor is directly proportional to a wrong attribute generation in the MDD model
Measurement procedure	The attributes to be measured must be counted to obtain the number of informational resources that cannot be transformed into attributes

Following, the formula to obtain the measure M1 – WAG is presented:

$$WAG_{nr\ resources} = conv\ M(\text{relatedToActor}(r) \text{ relatedToPhysResource}(r))$$

$$Conv(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \text{ is true} \\ 0 & \text{if } x \text{ is false} \end{cases}$$

M2. Wrong Service Generation (WSG). *Rationale.* According to the transformation guidelines, the tasks that do not generate entities (physical resources or actors) or that do not affect resources are transformed into services of the class generated from the owner actor (according to the corresponding actor

boundary). Therefore, if the corresponding actor is not marked for the generation of the intended system, the involved task cannot be transformed since it is not possible to generate a service in the class model without a class that contains it. See WSG characteristics in Table III.

TABLE III. MEASURE WRONG SERVICE GENERATION (WSG)

Characteristic	Definition
Measurement Entity	i^* model
Measurement Scale	Ratio scale
Attribute to be measured	Tasks that not generate entities nor affect resources and the related actor is not marked for the generation of the intended system
Measurement principle	A task that not generates entities nor affects resources and it is related to an actor not marked for the generation of the intended system is directly proportional to wrong service generation in the generated MDD model
Measurement procedure	the attributes to be measured must be counted to obtain the number of wrong services specified in the generated MDD model

Following, the formula to obtain the measure M2 – WSG is presented:

$$WSG_M = \frac{\text{conv}(\text{generatesResource}(t))}{\text{tasks}_M} \cdot \frac{\text{affectsResource}(t)}{\text{hasSystemActor}(t)}$$

M3. Non-Accessible Element (NAE). Rationale. According to the presented transformation guidelines (see Table I) agent relationships are defined between the classes generated from actors and the elements generated from services or informational resources contained in the corresponding actor boundaries. However, if the involved actors are not selected for the MDD model generation, the actor is not transformed in a class, and, hence, the involved agent relationships are not defined. This produces that the transformed tasks or informational resources (that are inside of the actor boundary) cannot be executed or visualized in the final application. However, it is not mandatory to define an actor as part of the intended system. For instance, the analyst could consider that the involved actor must not be maintained in the final system. In this case, a new agent (special user) must be defined at design time during the refinement of the generated class model to execute and visualize the generated elements, such as an administrator user. See NAE characteristics in Table IV.

TABLE IV. MEASURE NON-ACCESSIBLE ELEMENT (NAE)

Characteristic	Definition
Measurement Entity	i^* model
Measurement Scale	Ratio scale
Attribute to be measured	Internal tasks or resources related to the system that are defined in the boundary of an actor that is not related to the system
Measurement principle	An internal task or resource related to the system that is defined in the boundary of an actor that is not related to the system is directly proportional to the a non-accessible element in the generated MDD model
Measurement procedure	the attributes to be measured must be counted to obtain the number of non-accessible elements in the generated MDD model

Following, the formula to obtain the measure M3 – NAE is presented:

$$NAE_M = \frac{\text{conv}(\text{hasSystemActor}(t))}{\text{tasks}_M} \cdot \frac{\text{conv}(\text{hasSystemActor}(r))}{\text{resources}_M \cdot \text{informational}_M}$$

M4. Non-Instantiable Class (NIC). Rationale. The system entities (physical resources or actors) without a production task related are transformed into classes without an instancecreation service (see Table I). The service that produces new instances of a class takes special relevance since without this service, the class is not properly defined (all the defined classes must be capable of generating their instances). However, the definition of production task for entities (actors or physical resources) is not mandatory since this issue does not prevent the appropriate transformation of the i^* elements. Thus, specific instancecreation services can be defined at design time for the classes generated without this kind of services. See NIC characteristics in Table V.

TABLE V. MEASURE NON-INSTANCIABLE CLASS (NIC)

Characteristic	Definition
Measurement Entity	i^* model
Measurement Scale	Ratio scale
Attribute to be measured	Actors and physical resources without a task their production
Measurement principle	An actor or a physical resource without a reproduction task is directly proportional to a non-instantiable class in the generated MDD model
Measurement procedure	The attributes to be measured must be counted the number of non-instantiable classes

Following, the formula to obtain the measure M4 – NIC is presented:

$$NIC_M = \frac{\text{conv}(\text{hasProductionTask}(r))}{\text{resources}_M} \cdot \frac{\text{conv}(\text{hasProductionTask}(a))}{\text{actors}_M \cdot \text{kind}(r) \cdot \text{Physical}}$$

B. Step 2: i^* Metamodel Statement

The second step corresponds to stating the target i^* metamodel, which must be defined according to the EMOF specification [33]. The use of EMOF is mandatory for the appropriate application of the considered approach for modeling language integration [29]. Therefore, we have defined the EMOF i^* Metamodel presented in Fig. 6 by taking into account the i^* guide v3.0 [34], and the metamodel related to the User Requirements Notation (URN) [35], which is a variant of the i^* Framework. This figure only shows the structural representation of the metamodel. Additional features such as derived values, constraints, and operations are not necessary for the application of the proposed verification approach, and, hence, they have been omitted to simplify the metamodel representation.

C. Step 3: i^* Verification Model Definition

The third step of the process consists in the definition of a verification model. This is an EMOF model that includes the

information required for the correct application of the measures (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. EMOF i^* Metamodel

The verification model must include those elements that are not present in the reference i^* metamodel, which are also relevant for the correct generation of the corresponding MDD class models according to the transformation guidelines presented in Table I.

Fig. 7. Verification Model and Mapping Information

Fig. 7 also shows the mapping information that indicates the correspondences among the elements of the verification model and the i^* metamodel.

D. Step 4: i^* Measures Specification

The fourth step of the process corresponds to the OCL specification of the measures, which must be included in the verification model. This specification is performed by considering the modeling information that is contained in the verification model. Fig. 7 shows the names and outputs of the different OCL rules defined. For the measure specification, we have applied the measure patterns presented in [36], specifically, the *aggregation* and *locator* patterns. The *locator*

pattern is used to identify the elements involved in the measure evaluation, and the *aggregation* pattern is used to return the

final value of the measure. A very useful aspect of the application of these patterns is that the i^* elements that must be fixed can be easily identified by means of the *locator* pattern. For instance, the OCL definition of the measure WAG is comprised by two OCL rules: the *WAGLocator* rule that identifies the corresponding resources by returning a Boolean value, and the *WAGAggregation* rule that returns the final measure result by aggregating those resources where the OCL rule *WAGLocator* returns true (see Table VI).

TABLE VI. WAG MEASURE SPECIFICATION IN THE OCL LANGUAGE

Measure	Subject of Measure	Alert Level
<i>M2: Wrong Attributes Generation (WAG)</i>	<i>i* Informational Resources</i>	<i>Critical</i>
Context: <i>VModel</i> :WAGAggregation() : Integer Body: result = self.ownedNode ->select(irs irs.ocliIsKindOf(SInfoR)) ->select(irs irs.WAGLocator()->size() + self.ownedNode ->select(act act.ocliIsKindOf(SActor)) .ocliIsTypeOf(SActor).ownedElement ->select(irs rs.ocliIsKindOf(SInfoR)).ocliIsTypeOf(SInfoR) ->select(irs irs.WAGLocator()->size())		
Context: <i>SInfoR</i> :WAGLocator() : Boolean Body: result = self.infoOf->isEmptv()		

In addition, since the proposed measures have been defined for verification purposes, we have introduced a new property in the measure specification, which corresponds to the alert levels. These levels are: 1) Critical, which indicates that the situation identified by the measure prevents the transformation of the corresponding i^* elements; and 2) Warning, which indicates that there is a modeling issue that can be fixed to

improve the class model generated. These alert levels are derived from the separation proposed for the definition of the questions related to the GQM application (see Step 1 of this section). Thus, WAG and WSG measures have a *critical* level, and NAE and NIE measures have a *warning* level.

E. Step 5: *i** Extensions Generation

In the fifth step of the process, the verification model and the OCL specification of the measures are used to generate the metamodel extensions that are necessary to integrate the proposed measures into the *i** framework. These extensions are implemented in a UML profile [37] (see Fig. 8).

In general terms, the UML profile generation consists in the generation of one stereotype for each class of the verification model, and the definition of one tagged value for each property (attribute or association end) that has not correspondence in the target *i** metamodel (non-mapped properties). In particular, for those abstract classes that have the child classes mapped to different classes of the *i** metamodel, only the extensions related to the child classes are represented (stereotype *Actor*). Otherwise, if the abstract and the child classes are mapped to the same class in the *i** metamodel, only the extension of the concrete class is represented (stereotype *SResource*) and the extensions related to the child classes are omitted (stereotypes *SPhysicalR* and *SInfoR*). Additionally, the abstract stereotype *SNode* is not represented since it does not introduces new properties or operations into the *i** metamodel.

Fig. 8. UML Profile to extend de *i** metamodel with verification measures

In the generated UML profile, the elements of the OCL specification must be changed according to the mapped elements of the *i** metamodel (see Fig. 7), and the generated stereotypes and tagged values. For instance, the specification for measure WAG is finally defined as follows:

```
Context: VModel::WAGAggregation() : Integer
Body: result = self.ownedNode
->select(irs|irs.isStereotyped(SInfoR))
  .oclAsTvbe(Resource)
->select(irs|irs.WAGLocator()->size() +
self.ownedNode
->select(act|act.oclIsKindOf(Actor)).oclAsTvbe(Actor)
.ownedElement
->select(irs|irs.isStereotyped(SInfoR))
  .oclAsTvbe(Resource)
->select(irs|irs.WAGLocator()->size()

Context: SInfoR::WAGLocator() : Boolean
Body: result = self.infoOf->isEmptv()
```

It is important to mention that the OCL operation *isStereotype* is not part of the OMG specification and it must be defined or implemented according to the OCL interpreter used. For instance, in ATL this operation can be implemented as follows:

```
helper context UML|Element def : isStereotyped(name:String):Boolean =
not self.getAppliedStereotypes()->select(s|s.name=name)

->isEmptv():
```

Finally, for the definition *i** models extended with the generated UML profile, we have used the eclipse UML2 project. Thus, we take advantage of the already implemented

support for UML profiles that this tool provides. However, since there is a dependency between the UML profile application and the UML metamodel, we need to introduce a little adaptation to the defined *i** metamodel in order to use the implemented UML profile extension capabilities. This adaptation consists in the definition of two generalization relationships from the classes *IsModel* and *IsElement* of the *i** metamodel to the classes *Model* and *Element* of the UML metamodel, respectively.

V. APPLYING THE *i** VERIFICATION MEASURES

This section exemplifies how the proposed *i** measures are used to verify and improve the generation of the corresponding class model (see Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Process for the application of verification measures.

To specify the *i** models, the corresponding EMF editor has been generated by using the *i** metamodel that has been defined as reference. In order to improve the understanding of the *i** models presented in this paper, the pictures of these models corresponds to manual transcriptions of the defined EMF models using the *i** notation. Therefore, the example *i** model presented in Fig. 1 has been extended with the information that is required for the automatic measures application. Fig. 10 shows the *i** model extended with the generated UML profile.

Fig. 10. Example *i** Model extended with the generated UML Profile.

Only those *i** elements related to the intended system are considered in the transformation process. These elements are the stereotyped elements. Table VIII shows the values related to the tagged values of each stereotyped element.

TABLE VII. TAGGED VALUES RELATED TO THE EXAMPLE *i** MODEL

TaggedValue	Value	TaggedValue	Value
Curriculum		Photographer Price	
.infoOf	--	.infoOf	Photographer Level

Photo Equipment		Pub. House Price	
.infoOf	--	.infoOf	Photographer Level
PersonalData		Assign Required Equipment	
.infoOf	--	.affects	--
Reception Date		.generates	--
.infoOf	Work Request	Assign Date and Number	
Serial Number		.affects	Work Request
.infoOf	Work Request	.generates	--
Assign Photo Price		Assign Level	
.affects	--	.affects	--
.generates	--	.generates	--
Present Work Request		Refuse Work Request	
.affects	--	.affects	--
.generates	Work Request	.generates	Refused Work Request
Receive Work Request		Accept Work Request	
.affects	--	.affects	--
.generates	Work Request	.generates	Accepted Work Request

Table VIII shows the results obtained from the measures evaluation by indicating: 1) the result of the measure (the values obtained from the *aggregation* OCLs); and 2) the *i** elements that return *true* for evaluation of locator OCLs.

TABLE VIII. RESULTS OBTAINED FROM MEASURES EVALUATION.

Measure	Alert	Result (Aggregation)	Locator
WAG	Critical	3 Resources	Curriculum, Photo Equipment, Personal Data
WSG	Critical	3 Tasks	Assign Photo Price, Assign Required Equipment, Assign Level
NAE	Warning	15 Elements	All stereotyped informational resources and tasks defined in actors' boundaries (none stereotyped actors in the model)
NIC	Warning	1 Entity	Photographer Level

Fig. 11 shows the class model that may be generated from the example *i** without considering the information reported by the verification measures.

Fig. 11. Class model generated from the example *i** model

In Fig. 11 can be observed that those elements identified by the critical measures are not present, such as the resource *Curriculum* or the task *Assign Photo Price*. Therefore, it is

necessary to improve the defined *i** model in order to assure the transformation of all the selected *i** elements, i.e.; to fix the issues related to elements identified by critical measures.

A. Improving the *i** Models for MDD Model Generation

The results obtained from the measures application provide useful information to fix the detected modeling issues. Thus, it is possible to identify specific fixing guidelines for each measure formulated. For the four measures defined, the alternative guidelines presented in Table IX have been inferred.

TABLE IX. FIXING GUIDELINES RELATED TO THE VERIFICATION MEASURES

Measure	Wrong Attribute Generation (WAG)
Guidelines	Associate the informational resources to a system entity (stereotyped actor or physical resource).
	Change the kind of the informational resource to <i>physical resource</i> .
	Remove the resource from the intended system (unstereotyped resource).
Measure	Wrong Service Generation (WSG)
Guidelines	Define the owner actor as part of the intended system.
	Indicate if the involved task participates in the generation or affect the state of a system entity (stereotyped actors or physical resources).
Measure	Non-Accessible Element (NAE)
Guidelines	Define the owner actor as part of the intended system.
	Change the informational resource to <i>physical resource</i> .
Measure	Non-Instantiable Class (NIC)
Guidelines	Define a new task in the model as production task of the involved entity (stereotyped resource or physical resource).
	Indicate a task that is already defined in the model as production task of the entity (stereotyped resource or physical resource).
	Change the physical resource to <i>informational resource</i> .

In addition to the guidelines presented, it is also possible to remove the corresponding element from the intended system (i.e.; remove the stereotype), or even remove the element from the *i** model.

However, independently of the guidelines that can be derived from the different verification measures, this information is just a reference and the analyst is who must decide the guidelines to apply to improve the *i** model. Fig. 12 shows the *i** model improved by the analyst after analyzing the results obtained from the application of the verification measures.

In the improved *i** model, the task *Assign Level* affects the state of the new defined actor *Accepted Photographer*. The tasks *Assign Photo Price* and *Assign Photo Equipment* are now related to the resource *Photographer Level*. Another interesting change is the specification of the actor *Req. Photo Equipment* as informational resource. Even though this resource has not been located by the verification measures, the analyst has decided that it must be included in the system as part of the *Photographer Level*.

The informational resources located by the WAG measure are now defined as information of the actor *Photographer*. The warning related to the NIE measure has been solved by defining the task *Establish Level* as a generation task for the resource

Photographer Level. Table X shows the tagged values that have been changed in the improved i^* model.

Fig. 12. Improved i^* model

It is important to note that solving the issues identified by the verification measures, the stereotyped elements are properly performed, but also, an improved and detailer requirement representation is obtained. Fig. 13 shows the class model generated from the improved i^* model.

TABLE X. TAGGED VALUES CHANGED IN THE IMPROVED i^* MODEL

TaggedValue	Value	TaggedValue	Value
Curriculum		Assign Required Equipment	
.infoOf	Photographer	.affects	Photographer Level
Photo Equipment		.generates	
.infoOf	Photographer	Assign Level	
PersonalData		.affects	Accepted Photographer
.infoOf	Photographer	.generates	--
Req. Photo Equipment		Establish Level	
.infoOf	Photographer Level	.affects	--
Assign Photo Price		.generates	Photographer Level
.affects	Photographer Level		
.generates	--		

Fig. 13 shows that the class model generated from the improved i^* model has a more detailed system specification. Essential elements generated from the improved i^* model are the classes *Photographer* and *AcceptedPhotographer*. Also, associations among classes have been generated. In summary, all the stereotyped elements of the i^* model have been transformed to

conceptual constructs of the target class model. Thus, the MDD model represents all the system requirements considered.

Since the generated class model is an initial MDD model, it must be refined at design time. Some possible refinements are the specification of the specializations that exist between the class *PhotoWorkRequest* and the classes *AcceptedWorkRequest* and *RefusedWorkRequest*. Also, the cardinality of the associations and the appropriate specification of the services must be defined.

Fig. 13. Class model generated from the improved i^* model

In the improved i^* model, there still exist warning issues related to the NAE measure. These warning issues are derived from the stereotyped resources and tasks that are defined inside of the boundaries of the actors *Production Dept.* and *Commercial Dept.*, which are not considered as part of the system-to-be by the analyst. In this case, the analyst has considered that an administrator user must be specified at design time to visualize and execute the corresponding resources and tasks. However, since the NAE measure is just a warning measure, it does not prevent the correct transformation of the i^* model. It just indicates that the MDD constructs obtained from identified elements must be refined at design time to obtain a complete specification.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The integration of i^* models for requirements elicitation in MDD process is a step beyond going from Model-Driven Development (MDD) to Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) [38], where different modeling approaches can be integrated to obtain improved software products [26]. This paper has presented new results in this direction by introducing a process for the definition and integration of verification measures into the i^* framework. The main advantages of the proposed verification approach are:

- 1) *The verification measures assure the completeness of the generated MDD models in relation to the requirements and improve the completeness in relation to the system functionality.*
- 2) *The definition of the verification measures is driven by a systematic process that supports the correct identification of the elements to be verified.*
- 3) *The evaluation of the verification measures is automatic, which implies a time and effort reduction with respect to manual verifications.*
- 4) *Specific alert levels are defined to distinguish the i^* constructs that must be fixed from the i^* constructs that can be improved.*

5) *The definition and implementation of the verification measures is performed by using current open-source technologies and standards.*

Thus, using our proposal, the defined analysis models are not just documentation artifacts; they also play an active role in the development process by providing an entry point for the definition of the necessary MDD models. Additionally, according to the results obtained from the *i** and OO-Method integration, the use of *i** models facilitates the refinement of design models, providing a clear vision of the purpose of the modeled systems.

We are aware that additional evaluation of our proposal to real development scenarios is necessary. Therefore, we consider as future work the development of more empirical studies to validate the effectiveness of our approach and to obtain results about the benefits of using *i** models in real MDD processes. Additionally, we have planned to publish the complete suite of transformation guidelines and verification measures defined for *i** and OO-Method, which can be used as reference by different MDD approaches. Also, the *i** softgoals and their role in generating non-functional requirements to be considered in the MDD process are subject of ongoing work.

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